

**The Pastoral
Counsellors**

JOURNAL OF NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

In Collaboration With

Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies

and

Department of Guidance and Counselling
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

Volume 4 January 2025

ISSN: Print 2971-5199 Online 2971-5202

Editors in Chief

Prof Samson FATOKUN
Prof Donald ODELEYE

Managing Editors

Prof Isaiah ABOLARIN
Assoc. Prof Adekunle OTUNLA
Dr. Olabisi Precious T. KILLIAN
Dr. Tayo ADEYANJU

Corresponding Editor

Dr. Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI

The Effects of Broken Home on Adolescents' Academic Performances in Selected Senior Secondary Schools in Akinyele Local Government Area, Moniya, Ibadan

Samuel Oluwaseyi ONIOSUN

Department of Religious Studies, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

soniosun@gmail.com, +2348038551717

Ayodele A. ATOWOJU, PhD

Department of Religious Studies, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

atowoju.ayodele@lcu.edu.ng, +2348036726849

Abstract

This paper investigates the effects of broken home on Adolescents' academic performances in selected senior secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government Area, Moniya, Ibadan. Broken home is not an uncommon experience in human history, it is experienced by couples irrespective of their religion, academic, political, economic background etc. One of the most hit in the saga of divorce are adolescents born into the broken home. The study was conducted among senior secondary school students, 100 students were randomly selected from 10 secondary schools, making a total of 200 respondents. A questionnaire was adopted to obtain information from the respondents, and their terminal results was also looked at, using the descriptive research design, findings show that, students from broken homes suffer academic and emotional challenges and they usually perform poorly in their academic activities. It suggested that several of the elements that create poor academic performances associated with a separation such as family's income, trust issues, and uneasiness between partners, and this ought to be curtailed in order to lessen the chance of a shattered household. Adolescents from broken homes should be properly monitored, secured and controlled by the teachers and parents ought to be educated on the importance of remaining married as partner, in order to have a decent home, there must be endurance in the marriage.

Keywords: Broken Home, Adolescents, Academic Performance, Family, Secondary School, Akinyele Local Government

Introduction

The common marriage covenant vow "until death do us part" seems to many people an obsolete and unrealistic phrase. The marriage covenant "for better or for worst" has now changed to "for better for stay, for worse for run". The spirit of endurance is no more in today's marriages and this has opened doors for high rate of divorce among couples. Since there cannot be divorce without marriage, Scott (2012) states that marriage as an institution ordained by God to be a permanent, indissoluble life-long covenant relationship and union between a man and a woman for the purpose of fulfilling an innate need for community and procreation. Procreation and companionship are the basic twin purpose for marriage.

In recent times, the ever-increasing number of divorces have been posing a serious threat to the marriage institution which is valued very highly by all human cultures and religious traditions. Dominion (2003) explained that a careful examination of the contemporary nature of marriage well reveal the exact change. Hence, a healthy family is imperative for a healthy society and church at large. Christians, traditions, Islamic religious generally have certain ways of conducting marriages and how such marriages are expected to be guided by certain rules and regulations of such faiths. It is therefore true that people in all cultures and in all ages have considered marriage as a natural gift to humanity. It can be said with certainty that the institution of marriage is one that is natural and common to all human kind.

In the past, it was the belief of people that couple should stay in their marital union even if it is unpleasant, this they do for the sake of their children (Danfulani, 2001). But in more recent years, people began to reject the idea that divorce was pathological, destructive or harmful to the children. Marriage came to be seen as “a partnership of autonomous individual who could dissolve their relationship wherever they wished. This has made marriage to be treated as business contract which when started could still be stopped if one is fed up or the contract is becoming unprofitable (Leigh, 2007).

Marriage as God designs it is a living organism, A successful marriage does not happen by means of miracle alone. It needs to be fed and nurtured at all times, if this fails, the consequences are that the joyful mood of marriage will turn sour, thereby making the relationship to wither and die with many negative effects.

According to Danfulani (2001) affirmed that “The greatest tragedy in a marriage is separation or divorce which puts an end to the family relationship. Many homes are either facing trauma of divorce or its threat. All the aroma and the religious reference which the institution is known for will become a bygone issue if marriage is no longer taken seriously. It is upon this fact then that this research undertakes to investigate the impacts of broken home on adolescents’ academic performances using Akinyele Local Government, Moniya, Ibadan as a case study.

Concept of Broken Home

Family is the first institution where one starts to equip oneself to grow (Laldanmawia, 2013). It is the most important socio-cultural and psychological dynamism of history and of society. The dynamisms include such vital functions as the reproduction of population, being an economic system, cultural transmission, children to social life (Guler and Erkal, 2013). Children gain these dynamisms and the five basic functions of the family system in the home atmosphere. The five basic functions are the resolution of problems, communication in the family, distributing of roles in the family, responding emotionally and involving in emotions, and behavioural control. Children raised in families achieving a balance in those five basic functions and in dynamisms, being able to display flexibility when needed, and adapting into changes generally receive good education, they socialize, and gain a healthy personality (Guler and Erkal, 2013). Makinde (2004) asserts that the function of family is to provide happiness, security, cultural growth, and development of a sense of responsibility for enhancing continuity and societal perpetuation. However, when the home is broken, these functions are truncated.

According to Laldanmawia (2013), to be broken in the family, there must be some crises which are arisen out of misconception, mistreating, misunderstanding, misacceptance, etc. the occurring crises lead to the divorce of parents, disposal of sons or daughters and leaving home by any members of that family. It is controversial that whether to claim every splitting up is broken family, while they still run the family well. There are many families without father, mother, and other members but still conditionally and systematically running. They may not like to call them broken. Of course they are not broken, rather just some members left away.

Broken homes refer to families in which the parents are either divorced or separated. Causes of broken homes could be either natural or human induced factors. The natural factor is death of spouse; while the human induced factors include divorce and separation of mates. Causes of divorce, according to Arowolaje (2013) includes lack of time for partners in the relationship; keeping of extra marital partners; treating the other partner as a slave; lack of compatibility and unnecessary involvement of in-laws on marital affairs, there can be no divorce without a cause or causes, there are factors that leads to divorce. Kasoma (2012) and Kalimaposo (2008) also highlight the most common reasons for divorce, in African society which include:

1. **Economic Factor:** Many divorces are caused by economic factor, economic hardship, joblessness and poverty can bring conflict between husband and wife. When they are unable to manage their finances well, a partner may become suspicious of another because he or she conceals information on how money is being spent and this can drive them apart.

2. **Childlessness:** Childless is a factor for quick divorce among couples, a husband can divorce his wife and marry another in order to have children, a childless woman is looked down upon with same and abuse. The husband of such woman will not be satisfied with her no matter what she offers him, but the fact still remains that she cannot give birth to children. A wife can also be divorced if she fails to give birth to male children. This tells that giving birth to children is of higher importance than the marriage relationship itself.
3. **Denying Sex to the Other Partner:** Sex starvation was discovered to be one of the reasons why divorce has increased amongst couples. Some women are very spiritual and claim to be praying and fasting every day. This makes the man uncomfortable and he calls for a divorce, some of the women also usually claim to be going to church or mosque for a night vigil, simply to deny their husband sex. The man endures but gets to a point where he feels that he needs to get another wife and divorce his current wife.
4. **Chronic Domestic Violence:** The continuous abuse of a partner may result in divorce. A situation where one partner persistently maltreats the other partner is known as domestic violence. This maltreatment may be physical or sexual. In physical violence, there is the beating of a partner, slapping and kicking. Whereas, in sexual violence, there is the rape of a partner.
5. **Poor Communication:** This factor is one of the factors that is affecting couples. Inadequate or poor communication make the couples unable to understand each other, they cannot share information, feelings and decisions together, they cannot express themselves to each other. This can develop constant disagreement resulting in hateful and vengeful attitudes towards each other.
6. **Choosing of Wrong Marriage Partner:** Since it has become easy for young men and women to marry, many of them just choose their marriage partners without proper examination. No quality time to pray, inability to look into the family they wanted to get married from.
7. **Emotional Factor:** In a survey conducted by Messiger in 2006, Schell Robert submits that, emotional immaturity was discovered to be one of the causes of divorce. An inexperienced husband or wife may cause divorce, an immature person is proud, stubborn, insecure, dependent, and inconsiderable and temperamental.
8. **Parental Interference:** The trend suggest that people are getting more and more involved in their children's marriage. They sometimes make demands which are excessive and certainly very difficult to meet. Some are domineering and which like to rule in their children's marriage. Some parents encourage their daughters to marry rich men. This is marrying for ulterior motives rather than love. This trend is very common in African countries.

Concept of Adolescent

Adolescent is the transitory phase between childhood and adulthood (WHO), which is between ages 10 and 19 years. This stage involves a profound amount of change in all domains of development – biological, cognitive, psychological, and emotional. Personal relationships and settings also change during this period. There are three stages involved, which includes; early stage (10 – 13 years), Middle stage – (14 – 16 years), and Late stage – (17 – 19 years).

Concept of Students' Academic Performance

Academic performance is the focal point of every educational institution, irrespective of level and location, because the major index for appraising progress of educational institution is the students' performance, and the education curriculum of the society. The term 'academic performance' has been described as the scholastic standing of a student at a given moment. It refers to how an individual is able to demonstrate his or her intellectual abilities. This scholastic standing could be explained as the grades obtained in a course or

groups of courses taken (Asaolu, 2003). Thus, in predicting academic performance, the use of grades in examinations and reported that grades could serve as prediction measures and criterion measures (Adeyemi, 2008). According to Ward, Stoker and Murray-Ward (1996), academic achievement or performance is the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their short or long-term educational goals. It is commonly measured through examinations. However, there is no general agreement on how it is best evaluated or which aspects are most important – procedural knowledge such as skills or declarative knowledge such as facts.

Several factors influence students' academic performance. These include individual differences, cognitive factors such as attention, memory, and reasoning, non-cognitive factors such as attitudes, behaviours, and strategies, motivation, self-control, and extracurricular activities (Friedman & Mandel, 2011).

- i. **Individual Differences Factors:** Individual differences in academic performance have been linked to difference in intelligence and personality. Student with highly mental ability as demonstrated by IQ tests and those who are higher in conscientiousness (linked to effort and achievement motivation) tend to achieve highly in academic settings. Children's semi-structured home learning environment transitions into a more structured learning environment when children start first grade. Early academic achievement enhances later academic achievement. Parent's academic socialization is a term describing the way parents influence students' academic achievement by shaping students' skills, behaviours and attitudes towards school.
- ii. **Cognitive Factors:** Cognitive factors or learning factors are the extent to which a person's individual capabilities can influence their academic or learning performance. These factors include cognitive functions like attention, memory, and reasoning. Cognitive factors are often measured through examinations; college admission boards use standardized test such as the SAT and ACT when evaluating prospective candidates. Under grading students with high academic performance present mature learning beliefs, and a strong knowledge integration.
- iii. **Non-cognitive Factors:** Non- cognitive factors or skills are a set of "attitude, behaviours, and strategies" that promotes academic and professional academic and professional success, such as academic self-efficacy, self-control, motivation, expectancy and goal setting theories, emotional intelligence, and determination, the term serves as a distinction of cognitive factors, which are measured by teachers through tests and quizzes. Non-cognitive skills are increasingly gaining popularity because they provide a better explanation for academic and professional outcomes.
- iv. **Motivation:** Motivation is the reason behind an individual's actions. Research has found that students with higher academic performance, motivation and persistence use intrinsic goals rather than extrinsic ones. Furthermore, students who are motivated to improve upon their previous or upcoming performance tend to perform better academically than peers with lower motivation. In other words, students with higher need for achievement have greater academic performance.
- v. **Self-control:** Self-control in the academic setting is related self-discipline, self-regulation, delay of gratification and impulse control. Self-control is the capacity for altering one's own impulse control. Self-control is the capacity for altering one's own responses, especially to bring them into line with standards such as ideals, values, morals, and social expectations, and to support the attainment of long-term goals. In other words, self-control is the ability to priority long-term goals over the temptation of short-term impulses.

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory

This theory was formulated by Albert Bandura. The theory specifies that separation and divorce is caused by the relationship of partners as well as the impact of important person in their respective lives, is a

psychological theory that explains how people learn behaviours, attitudes, and values by observing and imitating others, According to Albert Bandura (1977), social learning theory, disagreement within union is on the shoulders of both partners, it stated that partners who interact must have responsibility for any matrimonial problem that arises in the context of marriage. This theory can help in reshaping behaviour, attitudes, and relationship within the family context, it provides a framework for promoting healthier family dynamics and reducing negative behaviours that can arise from broken homes.

However, Social learning theory has been useful in explaining how people and children can learn new things and develop new behaviours by observing other people, when the parents are well behaved and fully aware that their children will look unto them as a role model, they should possibly manage their home for benefit of their children and it will facilitate children attention, retention, reproduction, and as well as a source of motivation for them in school.

Methodology

This research adopted descriptive survey design and mixed-methods approach data collection techniques, that is qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques. The researcher used mixed-methods to analyse and describe the impacts of broken homes on adolescent's academic performances in selected secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government.

Findings and Discussions of Findings

Ten (10) secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government, Moniya were visited by the researcher, students and teachers were interviewed and the results of terminal examinations was also looked at.

Broken home has significant effect on student academic performance. Broken home hinders students' punctuality and present in the school and the classrooms, it also hampers calmness, physically and emotionally stable of students, students' attentiveness in the classroom are also deters by broken homes, and students from broken homes seldom meet up with essential academic needs. These indefinitely affect academic performance of students from broken homes in secondary school in Akinyele LGA. Moniya, Ibadan, as a case study.

This study also revealed the common side effect of broken home on students' academic performance. These include lateness to school and classroom, non-challant attitude towards academic endeavour, lingering mental development, lack of self-esteem, and poor interpersonal relationship. These posed threat to students' moral and academic performance in secondary schools in Akinyele LGA. Moniya.

In addition, it was discovered that female students are more devastated morally and academically as a result of broken home than the male counterparts, male students from broken homes are highly aggressive and unpreventable in their actions which also affects them academically, female students from broken homes are more attentive in the classroom than their male counterparts, female and male students from broken homes strive for achievement academically and morally compared with unbroken home students, and the academic performance of female students better than their male counterparts from broken homes.

Moreover, to overcome the challenges of broken home on students' academic performance, this study revealed the following strategies: group and family counselling on the need for family unity, regular and effective parental counselling on the effects of broken homes, provision of guidance and counselling to students from broken homes, guarantee of peaceful school and classrooms' atmosphere and climate for every student irrespective of the nature of their homes, and provision of assistance, in term of education materials, to students from broken homes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research has shown that students from broken homes often face more academic challenges compared to their counterparts from intact families. These challenges are not only reflected in their grades but also in their overall academic engagement, including participation in class, homework completion, and interest in learning.

This study looked into some factors that causes broken home, the concept of adolescent, and the students' academic performance. These include the level of parental involvement, the quality of the home learning environment, and the availability of resources for learning. It was found that in many broken homes, these factors are often compromised, leading to a less conducive environment for academic success.

However, it is important to note that divorce is the breaking of marriage relationship. Broken home encourages and breeds hooligans in the society as the caring parent could not cope with the upbringing of the children. It also aids immorality and child abuse which may damage the physical, emotional, and psychological wellbeing of the children. The society should have ethical concern to this in order to stop the ungodly characters in our society. The religious organizations can function in various ways such as nurturing, sustaining, reconciling, healing, guiding, motivating, and educating the affected children. They can also make available financial assistance to the children of divorced parents. Most children from these broken homes have their dreams aborted and future punctured as a result of divorce. Therefore, all efforts should be made to find a lasting solution to the problem of divorce in our society.

Recommendations

Having gone through the study of the effects of broken home on Adolescents' academic performances in selected senior secondary schools in Akinyele Local Government Area, Moniya, Ibadan, the followings are hereby recommended.

1. Adolescents from broken homes should be properly monitored, secured and controlled by the teachers and parents ought to be educated on the importance of remaining married to their partners, in order to have a decent home, there must be endurance in the marriage.
2. Schools should implement programs that provide emotional and academic support to students from broken homes. This could include counselling services, mentoring programs, and additional academic resources.
3. Teachers should be trained to identify and address the unique challenges faced by students from broken homes. This could include professional development workshops on topics such as trauma-informed teaching and social-emotional learning.
4. Schools should foster a supportive and inclusive environment where all students feel valued and accepted, regardless of their family situation.
5. Government and non-governmental organizations should provide financial assistance to families in need to ensure that students from broken homes have access to the same educational opportunities as their peers.
6. Schools should implement strategies to engage students from broken homes, such as peer mentoring programs or extracurricular activities that foster a sense of belonging.
7. Religious leaders should start organizing marriage seminars for married couples where they are taught about nonviolent approaches to conflict in the family. They should also be taught how to use negotiation, meditation, reconciliation and compromise in the midst of a disagreement.

References

- Adams, J. E. (2011). *Marriage, Divorce and Remarriage in the Bible*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan Publishing House.
- Adebimpe, P. Olusade (2011). "Marital Relationship, Compatibility and Conflict in Marriage in Abeokuta." Unpublished Master Thesis, Institute of African Studies, University of Ibadan.

- Adedeji, J. A. (2002). *The Marriage That Lasts*. Lagos: New Life Family Counselling Land Prayer Clinic.
- Ajila, C. & Olutola, A. (2000). Impact of parents' socio-economic status on university students' Academic performance. *Ife Journal of Educational Studies*, 7(1), 31 - 39.
- Anderson, Jan D. (1998). *Financial Problem and Divorce state in Marriage*. Boston: Hughton Milffin Company.
- Arowolaje, T. (2013). Five causes of broken homes. <https://www.thenationonlineng.net/new/five-causes-of-broken-homes>
- Asuquo P. N. and Maliki A. E. (2007), "Values Orientation and Marital Conflict Resolution: Implication for Marriage Counselling". *Stud. Tribal*, 5(1): 59-62.
- Ayodele, O. Samuel (1998). *Love, Marriage and Happy Family Life*. Ibadan: Powerhouse Press and Publisher.
- Azuka-Obieke, U. (2013). Single-parenting, psychological well-being and academic performance of adolescents in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies*.
- Dale, Ellerman. (2000), *Marital Conflict*. Tennessee: University of Memphis.
- Danfulani, Kore. (1995). *Culture and Christian Home*. Kaduna: Baraka Press.
- Dominion, J. (2004). *Dynamics of Marriage: Love, Sex and Growth from a Christian Perspective*. USA: Marriage Institute.
- Ebiere, G., & Dorgu, T.E. (2014). Influence of Family Structure on Students' Academic Performance in Agege Local Government Area, Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(26), 36-40.
- Hunter, Rodney. (2005). *Divorce, Children and Adolescents*. USA: Abingdon Press.
- Idowu, A. L. (2002), "The effects of Cognitive Restructuring in Resolving Marital Conflicts among Selected Couples in Ilorin," *Nigerian Journal of Applied Psychology*. Vol. 6. No. 1: 87-98.
- Lateju, Racheal. (2001). *The Effects of Divorce on Children and Church's response*. Ibadan.
- Leigh, Samuel Morakinyo, (1993). *Marriage Crisis: Promotion or Demotion*. Ibadan: Scripture Union, Nigeria.
- Marshall Smalley and Skorgrand Scot (1999). *Handbook of Marriage*. Chicago Rand McNally Company.
- Merman, Eleanor (2001). *The Cooperation of Family*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Nnaoma, I. (2013). The psycho-social effect of parental separation and divorce on adolescents: Implications for counselling in Surulere Local Government Area of Lagos State. *International Journal of Psychology and Counselling*, 5(7), 162-168.
- Schell, Robert. (2001). *Development of Psychology Today*. New York: Random House.
- Scott, A, (2001). *Divorce Prevalence and Implications of Divorce in Early America*. New York: Library Net.
- Shropshire, Marie (2002). Helping the Child of Divorce. *Home Life*, Lo. 40, 6.
- Tonybee, P. (2008). The Impact of Broken Homes on Children's Academic Performance. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*.
- Uwe E. A. (2000) "Marital Communication" *Marriage Counselling: Issues and Solution*, Calabar: Pyramid Publishers.